

Unified analysis of spatially-coupled absorption and saturation dynamics in multi-pass pumped thin-disk lasers

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Abstract: We present a theoretical framework that unifies pump absorption, gain saturation, thermo-optic distortion, and cavity diffraction into a self-consistent model of multi-pass pumped solid-state lasers. By deriving a theoretical formulation of the nonlinear coupling of the superimposed pump energy and effective absorption, we prove an unique steady-state solution exists. Applied to the multi-pass Yb:YAG thin-disk module, the framework is quantitatively validated with experiments, reproducing a well matched absorption tendency, errors in output power, beam diameter and M^2 within 3.0%, 1.7%, and 0.05 respectively. This approach provides predictive guidelines for pump-power scaling and pass-number optimization in high-power lasers.

1. INTRODUCTION

High-power solid-state lasers involve complex energy transfer between optical fields and gain media, where thermal and mechanical deformations of the optical elements strongly influence cavity dynamics [1–6]. Traditionally, laser output has been estimated by evaluating the population inversion derived from steady-state energy transfer equations. The conventional approach typically compresses diverse loss mechanisms into single effective terms and underestimating pump-beam distributions with approximate saturation effects. However, it is crucial to consider the coupled dynamics of pump absorption, saturation of gain and pump, and thermally influenced active media in high power regime [7–11]. While the prediction of signal power is sufficient from the energetics point of view, it is essential to accurately define the spatially overlapped pump energy when extending the model to two-dimensional (2D) intra-cavity optical fields. Moreover, a precise evaluation of the pump absorption is essential to theoretically derive the deformation of the medium and its effect on intra-cavity optical field evolution.

To address these limitations, we derive the absorbed pump power per pass in a self-consistent mathematical framework, extended to 2D intra-cavity fields. The formulation produces a unique fixed-point solution valid from single-pass to infinite-pass geometries, accounting for spatially accumulated energy, temperature-dependent cross-sections, and nonlinear saturation effects, which efficiently yield the pump-beam intensity distribution in the gain medium prior to reaching stimulated emission of the signal beam. To the best of our knowledge, this study presents the first comprehensive approach integrating spatial deformation, thermal effects, absorption, and emission of the medium as interdependent factors.

The formulation was first validated experimentally by measuring the unabsorbed parts from the Yb:YAG thin-disk module. Then, it is applied to the Yb:YAG laser system by combining measured disk optical path difference (OPD) maps with the rate equation to describe the cavity dynamics. The derived effective pump intensity with consideration of the medium temperature reproduces the absorption, signal power, beam quality and diameters in the experiment, demonstrating quantitative agreement with high-power resonator behavior.

46 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

47 *2.1. Theoretical approach*

48 The core of our approach is a self-consistent equation in which the locally accumulated pump
 49 energy and the effective absorption coefficient are determined simultaneously, fully coupling
 50 absorption-, gain-saturation, thermal effects, and spatial intensity distributions. Assuming
 51 monochromatic pumping into a medium of thickness L and cross-sectional area A_p , we define
 52 the steady-state effective absorption coefficient α_{eff} by equating the local pump-photon flux to
 53 the rate of ground-state depletion under steady-state rate equations. If saturation intensity is not
 54 considered, the absorption rate must be re-evaluated based on the signal oscillating within the
 55 cavity dynamics. Since this approach consumes significant resources in 2D field calculations, it
 56 is substantially efficient to derive the effective pump intensity when it is not lasing.

57 Saturation arises from changes in the level of population densities: stimulated emission depletes
 58 the excited-state while ground-state absorption depletes the ground-state [12, 13]. Because both
 59 processes act on the same atomic ensemble, any change in upper-state population that controls
 60 output power must concurrently affect pump absorption—even when the transitions occur at
 61 different wavelengths. Thermalization of the quantum-defect energy further alters line-widths,
 62 cross-sections and population distributions, reinforcing this mutual coupling [14, 15]. The
 63 absorption dynamics of Yb:YAG can be adequately described by a two-level system since rapid
 64 intra-manifold thermal relaxation instantaneously equilibrates the electronic population within
 65 each of the $^2F_{7/2}$ and $^2F_{5/2}$ manifolds. Here, excited-state absorption, cross relaxation and energy
 66 transfer upconversion are neglected due to the nature of ytterbium ion [16, 17]. At the steady-state
 67 temperature T_{ss} , α_{eff} is defined with saturation intensity in pump wavelength $I_{\text{sat}}^{(p)}$ and pump
 68 intensity I_p as follows.

$$\alpha_0 = N_0 \sigma_{\text{abs}}^{(p)}(T_{\text{ss}}), \quad \alpha_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\alpha_0}{1 + I_p / I_{\text{sat}}^{(p)}} \quad (1)$$

69 where $N_0 = N_1 + N_2$, total ion density, τ_f is the fluorescence lifetime, and $\sigma_{\text{abs}}^{(p)}(T_{\text{ss}})$ is the
 70 absorption cross-section at T_{ss} . Eq. (1) is called the absorption saturation effect derived from the
 71 population inversion equation (See Supplement 1.A), and effectively captures the reduction in
 72 the absorption rate induced by population inversion. In the steady-state response, the effective
 73 absorption α_{eff} must follow

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_{\text{eff}}}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (0 \leq \alpha_{\text{eff}} \leq \alpha_0) \quad (2)$$

74 The saturation intensity for the pump and signal wavelength (p, l),

$$I_{\text{sat}}^{(p,l)} = \frac{h\nu^{(p,l)}}{(\sigma_{\text{abs}}^{(p,l)}(T_{\text{ss}}) + \sigma_{\text{em}}^{(p,l)}(T_{\text{ss}}))\tau_f} \quad (3)$$

75 If one measures cross-section values, it inherently includes Stark-manifold averaging and
 76 re-absorption/re-emission corrections, which obviates the need for explicit modeling of individual
 77 Stark sublevels. Alternatively, one can derive theoretical values [8]. Note that, if only the
 78 absorption saturation effect is considered, the absorption saturation intensity should be derived
 79 based on the absorption cross-section. A uniform pumping energy $E_0 = \int P_0 dt$ per pass is
 80 transmitted and spatially overlapped on each traversal, yields the total overlapped energy E_{OL}
 81 after n_{pass} passes,

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{\text{OL}} &= E_0 e^{-\alpha_{\text{eff}} L} \sum_{k=0}^{n_{\text{pass}}-1} e^{-k \alpha_{\text{eff}} L} \\
&= E_0 e^{-\alpha_{\text{eff}} L} \frac{1 - e^{-n_{\text{pass}} \alpha_{\text{eff}} L}}{1 - e^{-\alpha_{\text{eff}} L}}
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

82 Simultaneously, the effective pump intensity I_{eff} is defined with spatially overlapped energy
83 and cross-sectional area A_p , which is ($I_{\text{eff}} = dE_{\text{OL}}/A_p dt = I_p$). The pump intensity in the gain
84 media depends on the number of passes and on the evolution of the local absorption coefficient α
85 that is considered as effective over one pass. This absorption coefficient itself depends on the
86 local intensity of the pump and on the number of the pass. To find the α_{eff} , a self-consistent
87 equation must therefore be solved. The self-consistent equations Eq. (5) is derived by Eqs. (4)
88 and (1), under steady-state response.

$$f(\alpha_{\text{eff}}, I_{\text{eff}}) = \frac{\alpha_0}{1 + \frac{I_{\text{eff}}}{I_{\text{sat}}} \frac{e^{-\alpha_{\text{eff}} L} (1 - e^{-n_{\text{pass}} \alpha_{\text{eff}} L})}{(1 - e^{-\alpha_{\text{eff}} L})}} \tag{5}$$

89 It highlights that the effective pump intensity and effective absorption coefficient α_{eff} follow
90 uniquely from a steady-state self-consistent formulation. The self-consistent equation is a non-
91 linear equation, and the absorption rate does not change in a steady-state while pumping the gain
92 medium. From Eq. (5), α_{eff} satisfies

$$\alpha_{\text{eff}} = f(\alpha_{\text{eff}}, I_{\text{eff}}) \tag{6}$$

93 The mapping $f(\alpha_{\text{eff}}, I_{\text{eff}})$ is continuous on the closed interval $[\varepsilon, \alpha_0]$ and satisfies $f([\varepsilon, \alpha_0], I_{\text{eff}}) \subseteq$
94 $[\varepsilon, \alpha_0]$. Moreover, $f(\alpha_{\text{eff}}, I_{\text{eff}})$ is strictly decreasing in α , with $f(0, I_{\text{eff}}) > 0$ and $f(\alpha_0, I_{\text{eff}}) < \alpha_0$.
95 By the intermediate value theorem, there exists a fixed point $\alpha_{\text{eff}}^* \in (0, \alpha_0)$ such that $f(\alpha_{\text{eff}}^*, I_{\text{eff}}) =$
96 α_{eff}^* . Monotonicity guarantees its uniqueness. Hence, one finite self-consistent pair $(\alpha_{\text{eff}}^*, I_{\text{eff}})$
97 exists for each $I_{\text{eff}} > 0$ (See Supplement 1.B for the detailed proof).

98 Under the uniform-field approximation, the absorbed pump intensity is obtained by integrating
99 the local absorption rate

$$\frac{P_{\text{abs}}}{A_p} = \int_0^L \alpha(z) I(z) dz \approx \alpha_{\text{eff}} I_{\text{eff}} L \tag{7}$$

100 so that $\alpha_{\text{eff}} I_{\text{eff}}$ denotes the local absorbed pump power density ($W \cdot m^{-3}$). From Eq. (1), the
101 absorbed power density is

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{A}(I_{\text{eff}}) &\equiv \alpha_{\text{eff}} I_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\alpha_0 I_{\text{eff}}}{1 + I_{\text{eff}}/I_{\text{sat}}} \\
&= \alpha_0 I_{\text{sat}} \frac{x}{1 + x} \quad \text{where} \quad x \equiv \frac{I_{\text{eff}}}{I_{\text{sat}}}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

102 which increases monotonically with I_{eff} and tends to the finite limit $\alpha_0 I_{\text{sat}}$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$. Hence,
103 although $\alpha_{\text{eff}} \rightarrow 0$ for very large I_{eff} , the absorbed power density does not vanish but saturates;
104 the absorbed power per unit area tends to $\alpha_0 I_{\text{sat}} L$ in the uniform field approximation.

105 In the low-absorption limit ($\alpha_{\text{eff}} L \ll 1$ i.e. low pumping intensity), admits a Taylor expansion
106 whose leading term yields the familiar linear scaling (Eq. (8)) reduces to the linear approximation

$$I_{\text{eff}} \approx \frac{P_0}{A_p} n_{\text{pass}} (1 - \alpha_0 L) \tag{9}$$

107 which validates the expressions employed in our analysis of multi-pass pumping [8–10]. In the
 108 limit $I_{\text{eff}} \gg I_{\text{sat}}$ (i.e., when the incident pump power is much larger than the saturation intensity
 109 or, equivalently, when the absorption cross section is very small), Eq. (8) reduces to

$$I_{\text{eff}} \approx \frac{P_0}{A_p} \times n_{\text{pass}} \quad (10)$$

110 Since achieving the condition of ($I_{\text{eff}} \gg I_{\text{sat}}$) is unattainable for the gain media of interest and
 111 practically undesirable, it is essential to derive a self-consistent pair (α_{eff}^* , E_{OL}^*). If we assume
 112 $n_{\text{pass}} \rightarrow \infty$, the E_{OL} in the medium can be defined as Eq. (11).

$$\lim_{n_{\text{pass}} \rightarrow \infty} E_{\text{OL}} = \frac{E_0 e^{-\alpha_{\text{eff}} L}}{1 - e^{-\alpha_{\text{eff}} L}} \quad (11)$$

113 Assuming a large number of passes, it is proper to derive the self-consistent pair (α_{eff}^* , E_{OL}^*)
 114 through Eqs. (11) and (1). Fig. 1(a) shows the experimental setup used to measure the unabsorbed
 115 pump beam in the 32 pass Yb:YAG thin-disk module. As seen in Fig. 1(b), the difference in
 116 effective pump intensity between relatively low and high incident intensities is clearly observed.
 117 The derived (α_{eff}^* , E_{OL}^*) demonstrate their effectiveness in the high-intensity pumping regime.

118 Pump photon flux (Φ_p) is derived by effective pump intensity $\Phi_p = I_{\text{eff}}/h\nu^{(p)}$. Pump photon
 119 flux, reflecting pump saturation effect and estimated Gaussian order shown in Fig.2(a), replaces
 120 the usual single-pass intensity in the quasi-three level rate equation defined by inversion ratio
 121 $\beta = N_2/N_0$. For quasi-three level media such as Yb:YAG, where the lower laser level lies near
 122 the ground-state and rapidly decays to it, thermal excitation partially repopulates the lower level,
 123 allowing a quasi-three level approximation [18].

$$\frac{d\beta}{dt} = -\gamma_{12}\beta + \left[(\sigma_{\text{abs}}^{(p)}(1-\beta) - \sigma_{\text{em}}^{(p)}\beta)\Phi_p + (\sigma_{\text{abs}}^{(l)}(1-\beta) - \sigma_{\text{em}}^{(l)}\beta)\Phi_l \right] \quad (12)$$

Fig. 1. (a) experimental configuration of measuring unabsorbed power measurement. (b) Typical calculation results of the absorption behavior with (Eq. (6)) and without saturation effects (Ideal absorption) for pump intensities of 1 kW/cm² and 4 kW/cm². Note pump intensity I_p is defined as the incident pump power divided by the pump beam area. Pump beam radius is 2.05 mm. Abbreviations are following; LD: laser diode, PM: power-meter and BS: beam splitter.

Fig. 2. (a) Experimental setup: simultaneous measurement of output power, disk wavefront during pumping. Typical example has been shown for the pump intensity of 4 kW/cm² (b) Temperature-dependent absorption and emission cross-section of Yb:YAG. (c) Typical example of simulated 2D distributions: temperature, inversion, and gain when pumping intensity of 4 kW/cm². Abbreviations as follows; WFS: wavefront sensor, LD: laser diode, PM: power-meter, BD: beam dump, PBS: polarized beam splitter and OC: output coupler.

124 where $\gamma_{12} = 1/\tau_f$ is the decay rate and Φ_l is signal photon flux $\Phi_l = I_l/h\nu^{(l)}$. Eq. (12) ensures
 125 that gain saturation, temperature dependent cross-sections, and spatial pump beam distribution
 126 are all captured. The absorption and emission cross-sections used in this equation are measured
 127 values corresponding to T_{ss} , as shown in Fig. 2(b). The I_{eff} is utilized for deriving pump photon
 128 flux, then small signal gain g_0 is derived via β

$$g_0(\beta) = N_0(\sigma_{em}^{(p,l)}\beta - \sigma_{abs}^{(p,l)}(1 - \beta))$$

$$G_D(\beta) = e^{(g_{eff}L)} \quad (13)$$

129 The intra-cavity signal photon flux (Φ_l) can be derived with effective small signal gain
 130 $g_{eff} = g_0/(1 + I_l/I_{sat}^{(l)})$, then used for deriving gain factor G_D . In our framework, the atoms
 131 participating in pump absorption and those contributing to stimulated emission are drawn from
 132 the same population, ensuring a consistent treatment of absorption and gain saturation. Rather
 133 than iteratively solving for absorption equilibrium within each field propagation step, we employ
 134 gain saturation to implicitly capture pump depletion. The resulting performance closely matched
 135 experimental observations, demonstrating the predictive power of the self-consistent model.

136 2.2. Roundtrip propagation

137 The derived photon flux is utilized to determine the precise distribution of the electric field
 138 $u(x, y)$ inside the cavity. The intra-cavity optical field arises from repeated amplification,
 139 diffractive propagation, and superposition of emissions the source [19, 20]. Thus, we assume
 140 single-unpolarized beams seeded by spontaneous emission. We chose the convenient seed term
 141 as $u_{in}(x, y) = u_{SE}(x, y)$, a spatially localized spontaneous emission source. For segment j
 142 of distance d_j , the combined propagation operator \mathcal{P}_j includes the Rayleigh–Sommerfeld diffraction
 143 \mathcal{R}_j and complex phase \mathcal{M}_j of the optics.

$$\mathcal{P}_j\{u(x, y)\} \equiv \mathcal{M}_j \circ \mathcal{R}_j\{u(x, y)\} \quad (14)$$

144 The disk-induced phase difference is defined in terms of the total surface profile $S_{D,\text{tot}}(x, y)$
 145 and the vacuum wavenumber k_0 as

$$\mathcal{M}\{S_{D,\text{tot}}\} = e^{-i \cdot 2k_0 \cdot S_{D,\text{tot}}} = e^{-i\Psi_D} \quad (15)$$

146 where Ψ_D is the OPD of the disk, capturing the effects of mechanical, thermal-expansion, and
 147 air convection, which are naturally accounted for the diffraction calculation [20, 21]. The surface
 148 deformation has been considered via factor 2 due to the reflection. The measured disk surface
 149 has been utilized for the disk-induced phase(see Fig. 2(a)). Composing the segment operators
 150 gives the round-trip operator \mathcal{T}

$$\mathcal{T}\{u(x, y)\} \equiv \mathcal{P}_N \circ \mathcal{P}_{N-1} \circ \dots \circ \mathcal{P}_2 \circ \mathcal{P}_1\{u(x, y)\} \quad (16)$$

151 After the k -th disk encounter the field is updated as

$$u_k(x, y) = u_{SE}(x, y) + \sqrt{\alpha_l \cdot G_D(x, y)} e^{[-i\Psi_D(x, y)]} \mathcal{T}\{u_{k-1}(x, y)\} \quad (17)$$

($k = 1, 2, \dots$)

152 where α_l is total intra-cavity loss including transmission of the output coupler 5% with cavity
 153 losses 1%. The circulating power after converging within the numerical tolerance represents
 154 $(\Delta P/\bar{P} < 0.001)$, $u_k(x, y)$ represents the steady-state intra-cavity field prior to output coupling.
 155 The intra-cavity field $u_k(x, y)$ evolves sequentially, as shown in Fig. 3(a).

156 2.3. Experimental details and numerical implementation

157 We first validated the approach by measuring the unabsorbed pump power (Fig. 1(a)) and
 158 subsequently confirmed it in single mode laser by comparing predicted and measured 2D output
 159 fields(Fig. 2(a)). The experimental setup was used with a 7.9%-doped, 188 μm -thick Yb:YAG
 160 disk, with pump intensities from 0 to 4 kW/cm^2 . The reconstructed pump profile from measured
 161 one (estimated super Gaussian of order 6) and in-situ disk surface deformation were used as
 162 inputs, while all other optical components were treated as ideal (Fig. 2 (a)). As shown in Fig.
 163 2 (b), measured absorption and emission cross-sections have been used [22], and applied to
 164 compute the initial 2D inversion and gain distributions (Fig. 2 (c)). Temperature distribution
 165 of the disk was computed using COMSOL Multiphysics by considering pumping intensity
 166 distribution with complex structure of the disk (diamond heatsink, disk bonding layer, and active
 167 medium), and validated against measured surface temperatures(Teledyne FLIR A65). From
 168 the measured cross-sections and temperature maps, 2D inversion and local gain maps can be
 169 calculated (Fig. 2(c)). The fluorescence lifetime (τ_f) is set as 0.95 ms for Yb:YAG, which does
 170 not show significant changes depending on the temperature of the medium, as shown in previous
 171 reports [23, 24]. Beam diameter was evaluated according to the ISO 11146 standard and the M^2
 172 parameter by deriving the covariance matrix [25, 26].

173 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

174 In this research, we compared unabsorbed pump power by the simulation, then applied the
 175 effective pump intensity into the gain medium to derive the signal intensity. The error in the
 176 absorption rate is maximum 3% in 1 kW/cm^2 pump intensity region, and it shows a well matched

Fig. 3. (a) Representative example illustrating the evolution of the intracavity wave. (b) Typical example of the output beam, simulated beam profile, phase and the population inversion ratio of the disk in the steady state. (c) Summary of results: comparison between experiment and simulation, where a radius of curvature of 40 m obtained from the wavefront sensor was applied. Unabsorbed ratio, output power, major beam diameter (D_{maj}), and beam quality factor (M^2) are compared. Note, ε_{abs} is difference of unabsorbed ratio between the experiment and derived value from Eq. (6), ε is relative errors and ε_{M^2} absolute errors between the experiment and measured OPD applied simulation results.

177 tendency as shown in Fig. 3(c). To eliminate this fundamental error in the low pump intensity
 178 region, the calculation needs to be spectrally resolved based on the population inversion ratio (β).
 179 Fig. 1(b) exhibits notably high non-absorption at high pump intensities. Such a high residual
 180 pump transmission is not observed in practical laser operation, since at the signal resonance the
 181 population inversion is reduced and the effective absorption coefficient correspondingly increases.
 182 Nevertheless, the proposed method practically provides an initial value for the pump-photon flux,
 183 enabling prediction of signal power, which assumes the monochromatic pump and monochromatic
 184 signal.

185 Numerical calculations were carried out to account for the phase change induced by the
 186 gain medium, considering (i) the ideal disk curvature $R = 40 \text{ m}$ and (ii) the measured surface
 187 deformation. The resulting phase profiles were then (iii) validated against the experimental data.
 188 Fig. 3(a) shows intra-cavity field evolution for case (ii). As shown in Fig. 3(b), the field-based
 189 approach enables the evaluation of the steady-state field, phase, and population inversion of the
 190 disk. The simulation incorporating the measured deformation of disk yields markedly

191 improved agreement with experiment (Fig. 3(c)). Quantitatively, the numerical model reproduces
192 output power within 3.0%, major and minor beam diameters within 1.7%, and M^2 within 0.05 of
193 the measured values. The small errors further underscore the validity of this approach. This
194 agreement validates the coupling of the derived self-consistency formula, rate-equation, and
195 propagation equation in the processing of 2D optical fields.

196 The actual pump-photon flux in laser operation cannot be obtained from a simple estimation,
197 because absorption and stimulated emission are dynamically coupled through the population
198 inversion. The field must be updated in the transient-state and the corresponding effective
199 absorption has to be calculated with amplified spontaneous emission (ASE), and temperature-
200 dependent level populations. Moreover, single-mode operation typically involves a pumped area
201 larger than the signal, producing spatial inversion inhomogeneity. Paradoxically, the substantial
202 complexity of deriving an accurate population inversion further highlights the practical utility of
203 the output predictions obtained with the method proposed here.

204 Two principal effects govern multi-pass performance in our configuration. First, effective
205 pump intensity depends non-linearly on intensity and pass number because the steady-state
206 absorption that enters the rate equation and the saturated gain that determines amplification
207 are mutually coupled; this coupling places a hard constraint on local intensities and implies
208 that improving efficiency requires either a medium with higher saturation intensity or greater
209 pump overlap with higher absorption rate. Second, because the pump profile and all other optics
210 are identical between cases, the $\approx 23\%$ reduction in achievable output at 4 kW/cm^2 pumping
211 relative to the ideal-curvature ($R=40 \text{ m}$) simulation is attributable to diffraction arising from
212 the measured disk deformation; this deformation is therefore the dominant source of mode
213 mixing and output loss under the conditions tested. The errors in output power between the
214 experiment and the simulation increase nonlinearly with pump intensity due to ASE, as previously
215 reported [27], yet the resulting discrepancy remains small because ASE is generated inside the
216 resonator and is effectively suppressed by the output coupler transmission. The experimental
217 validation underscores the importance of optimizing the gain medium curvature and pump beam
218 profile to realize the ideal disk geometry prerequisite for fundamental transverse mode operation.

219 4. CONCLUSION

220 We have developed and theoretically derived a self-consistent framework that couples
221 temperature-dependent absorption and gain saturation with cavity diffraction dynamics. This
222 theoretical approach effectively addresses the method for dealing with pump photon flux from
223 low- to high-intensity regime. The framework shows high fidelity to experimental results,
224 expanded into the cavity in 2D spatial domain. Applied to Yb:YAG, the framework reproduces
225 the absorption rate, output power, beam size, and M^2 in excellent agreement with the experiment.

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231 P. Sikocinski, Y. Levy and J. Mužík analyzed material property. P. Sikocinski, Y. Levy and J. Mužík carried
232 out the experiment. H. Jo wrote the manuscript. H. Jo, J. Mužík, P. Sikocinski and M. Chyla analyzed
233 the data. M. Smrž and T. Mocek provided the technical guidance and research supervision. All authors
234 contributed to the data collection, discussed the results, and reviewed the manuscript.

235 **Disclosures.** The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

236 **Data Availability Statement.** The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in
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238 **Supplemental document.** See Supplement 1 for supporting content.

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